

FAULT RECOVERY CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FAULT TOLERANT MULTI-PROCESSOR

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was made in the Avionics Integration Research Laboratory (AIRLAB) of the fault handling performance of the Fault Tolerant Multi-Processor (FTMP). Fault handling errors detected during fault injection experiments were characterized. In these fault injection experiments, the FTMP disabled a working unit instead of the faulted unit once every five hundred faults, on the average. System design weaknesses allow active faults to exercise a part of the fault management software that handles byzantine or *lying* faults. These weak areas in the FTMP's design increase the probability that, for any hardware fault, a good LRU is mistakenly disabled by the fault management software.

INTRODUCTION

The Fault-Tolerant Multi-Processor (FTMP) is a multi-computer system designed according to fault tolerant design principles to survive and continue operations after the occurrence of several non-simultaneous faults.¹ The intended application of the system design is flight critical applications where a high reliability is required to ensure the survival of the vehicle, crew, and passengers. The often stated reliability goal is expressed as a probability of failure of less than or equal to 10^{-9} for a 10-hour mission. An engineering prototype of the FTMP was constructed in the late 1970's and preliminary testing was conducted by the system designers.² Thereafter the system was delivered to NASA Langley where it has been subjected to more extensive experimentation.³

Early fault-injection experiments concentrated on obtaining recovery time data used to construct a recovery distribution from which certain parameters, which are required inputs of reliability assessment tools (e.g., SURE and CARE III), can be estimated. Also performed were experiments designed to measure or estimate fault latency and fault-free performance.

Early fault-injection experiments design methodology was straightforward, a pin was selected at random from a chip selected at random from a system board also selected at random. Other methods of selecting the fault injection

location, called sampling methods in ref. 3, had been devised and used to design experiments. These methods of selecting a location for fault injection assured compliance with statistical theory and thus accuracy in parameter estimation. The data acquisition requirements for these experiments were modest and were satisfied with the existing data acquisition system.^{3,4,5}

Selection of injection points at random over the whole system misses many weak points in the system which can be identified by careful examination and testing of the design. The common perception is that in order to explore the system for the existence of abnormal recovery behavior and single-point failures, exhaustive or *massive* fault injection testing must be performed.

A new methodology for fault injection experiments is proposed in this paper that enhances the probability of detecting abnormalities and inadequacies in a system. The results presented in this paper were obtained using the new methodology. These results support the contention that the new method enhances the probability of detecting inadequacies in fault-tolerant systems.

The new methodology is based on two principles: (1) faults should be injected mainly in signals with high fan-outs (e.g., board enables and other control signals), thus maximizing the the number of errors introduced into the system; (2) the information/data necessary to determine the system state should be observable at all times in real-time.

These principles, although seemingly simple, require a completely new experimental environment. The data acquisition requirements imposed by the new methodology on the FTMP test environment overburdened the original data acquisition system. This system was sufficient for the early work but completely inadequate for the new methodology and necessitated the design of a new system with three orders of magnitude improvement in data acquisition rates.⁵ The application of the new methodology to fault injection experiments uncovered an abnormal fault recovery behavior never observed before.

Experiments using the new data acquisition system were designed to characterize the mechanism by which a fault induced a non-faulted LRU to report an error not visible to others. Once the cause of the behavior was discovered and characterized an analytical model was developed

FIGURE 1. FTMP architecture.

using easily measurable parameters to estimate the probability that an abnormal recovery would occur during the process of recovering from a naturally occurring fault. Also, the model was used to estimate the probability of a general triple-modular redundant system suffering a recovery failure.

FTMP BACKGROUND

For a detailed description of the physical configuration of the AIRLAB FTMP testbed see ref. 1. There are 11 LRUs (12 LRUs is the maximum number of LRUs supported by the FTMP) which are interconnected by a redundant system bus. Each LRU contains a processor with cache, a system bus interface, and a system memory unit (there are many other subsystems which are not important to the subject of this paper and are therefore not mentioned).

At system restart, the processors and the memories are organized in triads (see fig. 1) to provide the redundancy required to tolerate a single fault anywhere in the system. The triads are tightly synchronized, i.e., all the processor (memory) components of a processor (memory) triad execute the same instruction (operation) on the same clock cycle. Thus synchronized, three copies of all input/output data from a triad are presented to the triple redundant system bus. The copies are then voted bit by bit to mask any errors that might occur due to a fault on any of the triad components and the detection is flagged by setting a bit in an error-latch.^{1,4}

Each LRU contains error-latches, each error-latch contains one bit for each bus available to the system. Setting the bit corresponding to one bus, for example, signifies that an error was detected in that bus during a previous transaction.^{1,4}

FAULT INJECTION EXPERIMENTS

Pin level fault injection experiments have been performed for the past several years on the FTMP testbed.^{2,3}

In these experiments, hardware fault injector systems use different methods to induce a temporary malfunction in one or more components of the target system.^{2,6} The errors resulting from the induced fault propagate through the circuits, thus producing erroneous behavior at the system bus level. Manifestation of the errors at this level occur by several *fault-to-system bus* error paths operating singly or simultaneously. For example, a fault can corrupt output data on cache or disable the system bus interface, or both; in such a case, the external behavior of the faulted unit will differ from the *normal*, as determined by voting the data presented to the system bus by the faulted unit and its two non-faulted triad partners.

ERROR-LATCH PROCESSING

Errors at the system bus level are flagged by setting the error-latches. The latches are read into system memory and processed every 320 msec by the fault management software.^{4,7} Error-latches are not redundant, each LRU contains one of every kind. Therefore, error-latch values are read with a *simplex read operation*, i.e., there is only one copy transmitted through one of the active R buses.

As a result of the simplex nature of the error-latch data, several tests are performed on the error data in system memory before it is considered by the fault management software. These tests are designed to filter out corrupted data. The R bus from which the corrupted error latch values were read is then marked suspect and any other values read through it are discarded. The identity of all the buses with errors, as accused by all the latch values that survived the consistency checks, are passed to the fault management software for isolation of the faulty component(s) (which could be the bus or any processor or memory unit enabled on the suspect bus).

A special case occurs when only one good error-latch indicates an error on an active bus. This situation is called the *lying-fault syndrome* in reference 6. In such a case the identity of the LRU from which the error-latch was read is stored in system memory. If the situation repeats with the same LRU, then the LRU is disabled (both the processor and the memory unit of that LRU are disabled).

ANOMALOUS BEHAVIOR

As mentioned in the introduction, during the analysis of the fault injection data it was noted that LRUs not being faulted were regularly disabled by the fault management software. Although the system classified the events as being caused by real permanent faults that occurred during the fault injection experiment, no evidence of these faults could be found after the fault injection experiment was completed. All the supposedly faulty units were reactivated either manually or by booting the system. Therefore, it was concluded that these events must be somehow caused by the faults injected during the experiments.

For experiments that lasted 4,000 faults or longer, 4 non-faulted LRUs are usually disabled before the system crashed. Obviously, whatever was causing the LRUs to fail did not disappear after the first LRU was disabled. Some discernible patterns in the data were observed. For example, in all the experiments where LRU 9 was not in the configuration (due to a real fault), LRU A was disabled first. In approximately 50 percent of the experiments the second LRU to be disabled was LRU 5 followed by LRU 8. In the other 50 percent, LRU 8 was second followed by LRU 5. The fourth disabled LRU was LRU 7.

With LRU 9 present (after being repaired) usually five LRUs are disabled before the system crashes. The first LRU to be disabled alternated randomly between LRUs 5 or A. The second LRU to be disabled would be either LRU 5 or A depending on who was first. The next casualty would then be LRU 9 and thereafter LRUs 8 and 7 would follow.

CAUSES OF ANOMALOUS BEHAVIOR

The data acquisition system monitored the buses for when the fault management software read the error-latches. The data thus obtained comes directly out of the latches and into the system bus. Subsequently, the locations where these values are stored in system memory were monitored. The data from both sources can be compared to determine if any value has changed. In order to reduce the data to be stored and analyzed, the acquisition system was programmed to sift through the acquired error-latch data and to store only those sets where bus errors are reported. These data clearly indicated that the error-latches were not being cleared by faulty software nor are the values corrupted during storage in system memory or during transit in the system bus.

The data indicated another possibility. The time between reading the last error-latch of LRU n and reading the first error-latch of LRU $n + 1$ (t_γ) varies depending on the number of transactions by other triads (typically 3 to 7) from 277 μsec to over 500 μsec . The time between reading error-latches of the same LRU (t_ρ), e.g., reading P bus and R bus error-latches of LRU 1, varies with the I/O traffic from 67 μsec to 250 μsec .

If LRU 9 is not in the configuration, a P bus error generated anywhere after the P bus error-latch of LRU 8 is read, but before the P bus error-latch of LRU A is, would be signalled only by LRU A. Although the error is detected by all the LRUs, the software read the error-latch values of LRUs 0 through 8 before the error occurred. So when LRU A's P bus error-latch is read, it is the only one that appears to the software as having detected an error. An event fitting this pattern was captured with the data acquisition system.⁴

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Using the average values for t_γ (304 μsec) and t_ρ (71 μsec), it is possible to estimate the probabilities that the

TABLE 1. VARIABILITY OF N_F .

m,n signs	N_F		
	$P_e = 1/310$	$P_e = 1/619$	$P_e = 1/929$
-,-	3017	6034	9051
-,+	649	1297	1946
+,-	1000	2001	3002
+,+	215	430	645

first bus error in the cycle occurs in the sensitive intervals.⁴ Assuming an error can occur at a random time within the cycle, then the event probability is, $P_e \approx 1/310$. With LRU 9 in the configuration, the same analysis gives a probability $P_e \approx 1/619$. Therefore, when LRU 9 absent, LRU A has double the chances of *lying*.⁴

Using the estimated probabilities it is possible to estimate the average number of faults injections before an LRU is disabled by the *lying-fault syndrome*. An LRU's probability of *lying* per 320 $m\text{sec}$ cycle (T) is P_e . The average fault is maintained for a period (F_t) of approximately 372.4 $m\text{sec}$. Therefore, the probability per fault is, $P_F = (F_t \div T)P_e = 1.16P_e$. Two *lying* events are required. Thus, the average number of faults is given by:

$$N_F = \frac{2}{P_F} = \frac{2}{1.16P_e} \quad (1)$$

Without LRU 9, LRU A's $P_e = 1/310$, therefore, the expected number of faults injected before the LRU is disabled is, $N_F \approx 534$. With LRU 9, LRU A's $P_e = 1/619$, therefore, $N_F \approx 1067$.

After LRU A is disabled, the same analysis applies for the active LRU whose error-latches are read last by the fault management software, e.g., if LRU A is the first LRU to be disabled and LRU 9 is not in the system, then, this same analysis applies to LRU 8 which results in a probability equal to 1/619 ($N_F \approx 1067$) of LRU 8 being the only LRU signalling a P bus error. A similar analysis applies to LRU 5.⁴

To account for the variability of the real process, the sample standard deviations of F_t ($\sigma_F = 120.3 m\text{sec}$), t_γ ($\sigma_\gamma = 53.5 \mu\text{sec}$) and t_ρ ($\sigma_\rho = 39.4 \mu\text{sec}$) are used to estimate a first order approximation to the variabilities of P_e and N_F . The equations are developed in ref. 4; the results (estimates of the 2σ bounds of N_F) are shown in table 1.

From table 1, the lower and upper 2σ bounds of N_F are:

$$\begin{aligned} 400 &\leq N_F \leq 6000 \text{ (with LRU 9),} \\ 200 &\leq N_F \leq 3000 \text{ (without LRU 9),} \\ 600 &\leq N_F \leq 9000 \text{ (for LRU 5).} \end{aligned}$$

A more useful set of bounds is obtained by setting the upper limits at 2000 with LRU 9, 1000 without LRU 9, and 3000

for LRU 5. Assuming the signs of the standard deviations are random and independent from the other parameters then these upper bounds will not be exceeded 75 percent of the time.

MODEL PREDICTIONS

Using this model it is possible to predict the expected sequence of LRUs that are disabled during a typical fault injection experiment. The sequence of LRUs disabled are derived based only on two conditions: the absence of LRU 9 and the expected number of faults (N_F). Using the average value of N_F to derive the sequence should lead to the most probable sequence. To derive the sequence it must be remembered that the LRU number is not important. The important information is the position that the LRU adopts in the sequence of error-latch read operations, i.e., the last active LRU in the sequence or the last LRU in the sequence which is a member of the triad containing the faulted processor.

The sequence of disabled LRUs is produced by computing and listing their N_F in increasing order. The re-configuration process must be taken into account in the calculations of N_F . For example: LRU A (with an average $N_F = 534$) is disabled first, followed by LRU 5 ($N_F = 1600$). After LRU A is disabled LRU 8 becomes the last active LRU in the latch reading sequence (as did LRU A). Therefore, when LRU A is disabled, LRU 8 starts *lying* and after the expected 1067 faults from this moment ($1067 + 534 = 1600$ faults from the beginning of the experiment) it is disabled. As suggested by their similar N_F , LRUs 5 and 8 frequently switch positions in the sequence. Following this procedure down until only one triad is present we obtain the desired sequence. There is no need to continue any further since the fault management software prevents any triad from reconfiguring itself. Therefore, being the only active triad in the system, it will not reconfigure under any circumstances.

The model's sequence of disabled LRUs, $A \rightarrow 5$ (or 8) $\rightarrow 8$ (or 5) $\rightarrow 7 \rightarrow$ system failure, is the most commonly observed (≈ 99 percent of the experiments). Other less probable sequences have been observed, all of them involve permutations of the $A \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 7$ sequence. If the variability of N_F is included, these less probable sequences result from the overlapping of the N_F values for the different LRUs.

In table 2 comparisons between experimental data and the model results are shown. General agreement exist between the model and the experiment's sequence of LRUs disabled and the number of faults injected before each LRU was disabled. In particular, when the variability of N_F is included, third column in table 2, all the LRUs were disabled in their predicted 2σ intervals 86 percent of the time.

TABLE 2. EMPIRICAL VS. MODEL RESULTS

LRU	EXPERIMENTS	MODEL
A	170 <444> ^a 1090	200 <534> 1000
5	790 <1280> 2290	600 <1600> 3000
8	760 <1370> 1990	600 <1600> 3000
7	2500 <3670> 5100	1000 <2668> 5000

^aLOWER 2σ LIMIT<AVERAGE>UPPER 2σ LIMIT

SOLUTION

Keeping control of the bus while the triad reads the error-latch information should prevent other triads from performing transactions during this time, thus preventing an error to occur between error-latch readings. Unfortunately, holding the bus does not solve the problem entirely, i.e., P_e does not become zero. Any error manifestation of a naturally occurring intermittent or transient fault in an element of the triad reading the error-latch values could propagate to the system bus at the appropriate time to cause the *lying-fault* behavior. In fault injection experiments a similar situation exists: the faults are injected at random times which therefore produce a non-zero probability that the fault will be injected at the appropriate moment when the faulted unit is a member of the triad reading the latches, thus causing the *lying* behavior. The faulted unit is re-enabled after each fault thus providing many trials on which a *lying* event could occur. Experiments were performed in which the system was modified to hold the bus during error-latch transactions and then subjected to fault injections. These experiments confirmed that the probability P_e is not reduced to zero by holding the bus.

Elimination of the behavior seems possible by the following procedure. After reading and analyzing the error-latches, and after determining there is *lying* event where LRU x is accusing LRU y of producing an error, the error latches of all the LRUs read before reading LRU x's latches should be read again. With this procedure the situation explained in this section is avoided, i.e., if an error occurred just before LRU x's latches are read, then reading the latches of all the LRUs read previous to the error event would yield the missing data and eliminate the appearance of a *lying* event. Unfortunately, this procedure extends the error-latch processing time by a factor of two, which causes frame slippage and other scheduling problems on the FTMP.

The most promising solution would seem to be redundant latches on the LRUs. Redundant latches would make all the present latch processing unnecessary, and, coupled with the above procedure for dealing with a single LRU reporting an error, would eliminate the processing overhead and the *lying* event problems.

IMPLICATIONS FOR THE FTMP

This section considers the effects of real faults on FTMP's behavior with the *lying* fault process taken into

TABLE 3. EMPIRICAL VALUES FOR p_n AND N.

Cycles (n)	p_n	
	HARD	INTERMITTENT ^a
1	.3525	0
2	.6187	.1277
3	.0288	.8298
4	0	.0425
N =	3	4

^aFor stuck-at-one faults injected at random times and lasting for 1 msec.

account. The emphasis here is to develop a model that combines the error production behavior of the faults and the system architecture into equations that can be used to predict the probability of observing this behavior for real faults. These equations can then be generalized and applied to more general architectures.

At the system bus level, a hard fault on the FTMP behaves as an intermittent fault, i.e., the fault-generated errors occur only when the faulty unit is on the bus. A hard fault is defined here as a fault which causes the affected LRU to generate an error every time it transmits on the bus. An intermittent or transient fault, in contrast, is defined here as a fault which causes the affected LRU to generate an error in a fraction (< 1) of its transmissions on the bus. Therefore, in the FTMP, the fault behaviors for hard, transient, and intermittent faults differ by the error production rate, with hard faults producing errors at the same rate that the faulty unit performs I/O operations while intermittent and transient faults produce errors at a fraction of the I/O rate.

HARD FAULTS

For hard faults there is only one chance for *lying* events to occur: the events must occur before the faulty unit is isolated and reconfigured out. Hard faults could be isolated in one or more cycles. If it takes only one cycle to isolate the fault, then the fault has only one chance of causing a *lying* event. During the first cycle, if the faulty LRU is disabled, the error-producing hard fault is taken out of commission before it generates another *lying* event. If the system takes longer than one cycle, then a chance exist that two *lying* events are generated in consecutive cycles. The parameters p_n (the probability that n cycles are required to recover from a fault) and N (the maximum number of cycles required to recover from a fault) can be estimated from fault injection data for both hard and intermittent faults. The results are shown in table 3.⁴

The rate at which a hard fault generates two *lying* events is given by equation (2),

$$R = 3\lambda P_e^2 [2p_2 + p_3(1 - P_e)], \quad (2)$$

where,

- R = Rate at which a *lying* LRU is disabled per hour,
- P_e = probability of a *lying* LRU per cycle,
- λ = hard failure rate for an LRU,
- p_n = probability that n cycles are required to isolate the fault ($n = 2$ or 3 for hard faults).

Equation (2), accounts for the fact that the fault management software moves from one triad to another on every cycle.

After the *lying* LRU is disabled, the faulty LRU is most likely disabled; therefore, R also gives the rate at which two LRUs are disabled, the *lying* and the faulty LRUs.

Computing R, using the values for a hard fault in table 3 and assuming a failure rate of $\lambda = 10^{-4}/hour$ and $P_e = 1/619$ we have, $R \approx 10^{-9}/hour$, i.e., the rate at which two LRUs are disabled (the first one due to a *lying* event and the second to the real hard fault) is approximately $10^{-9}/hour$.⁴

INTERMITTENT FAULTS

The error production behavior of intermittent faults is assumed to be random in time (although depending on where the fault is located, the utilization rate of the faulty hardware, and the faulty hardware's input signals), therefore, no consideration is necessary for the case where the faulty unit is part of the triad reading the error-latches. The rate for two *lying* events is given by equation (3) below.

$$R = 9\lambda \times \sum_{n/2}^N \left\{ p_n \times P_e^2 \times (1 - P_e)^{n-2} \times \frac{n!}{2!(n-2)!} \right\}. \quad (3)$$

For intermittent faults, it usually takes more than two cycles to isolate the faulty unit, as shown in table 3. Therefore, the rate for two *lying* events is greater for intermittent than for hard faults, which are isolated in one cycle 35.3% of the time. Computing R using the same value for P_e as before, $\lambda = 10^{-4}$, and using the values given in table 3 for p_n for intermittent faults gives $R \approx 6.7 \times 10^{-9}/hour$. For a rate, $R \leq 1 \times 10^{-10}/hour$, the intermittent failure rate must be, $\lambda \leq 1.5 \times 10^{-6}/hour$.⁴

HOLDING THE BUS

By holding the system bus it is possible to keep triads from executing transactions at the time when the error-latches are read, but if an element of the triad performing the latch read is affected with an intermittent fault, then there is a chance for the fault to generate an error at the appropriate times to generate a *lying* event. Under the

TABLE 4. FAILURE RATE BY LYING

P_e	R (Equation 11)
1.0×10^{-5}	8.6×10^{-14}
5.0×10^{-5}	2.2×10^{-12}
1.0×10^{-4}	8.6×10^{-12}
5.0×10^{-4}	2.2×10^{-10}
1.0×10^{-3}	8.6×10^{-10}
5.0×10^{-3}	2.1×10^{-8}
1.0×10^{-2}	8.5×10^{-8}
5.0×10^{-2}	2.0×10^{-5}

*R is in the same units as λ

same assumptions as above, then, the rate of a *lying* event caused by an intermittent fault is given by equation (4),

$$R = 3\lambda p_4 P_e^2. \quad (4)$$

The value of P_e when the system holds the bus differs from the previous value used above.⁴ The new value is $P_e = 1/700$.⁴ Evaluating equation (3) with this value of P_e , with $\lambda = 10^{-4}$, and with the appropriate p_n 's results in $R = 2.6 \times 10^{-11}/\text{hour}$ as the rate of losing an LRU to a *lying* event.⁴

LYING EVENTS ON A TMR SYSTEM

For a fault tolerant system based on adaptive voting Triple Modular Redundancy (TMR) principles, the probability of failure is \geq the probability of losing a good LRU while there is a faulty LRU active. For this situation, after the good LRU is disabled, leaving the faulty one to produce more errors, the system has enough redundancy to detect errors, but not enough to mask them. Thus, it is assumed that the next error causes a system failure. The rate for a *lying* event in a TMR system is given by equation (5),

$$R = 3\lambda \times \sum_{n/2}^N \left\{ p_n \times P_e^2 \times (1 - P_e)^{n-2} \times \frac{n!}{2!(n-2)!} \right\}. \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) is obtained from equation (3) by considering that in a TMR system there is only one *triad* that reads the error data. The system failure rate (R) versus the probability of a *lying* event (P_e) for a TMR system is shown in table 4 for different ranges of P_e and assuming $\lambda = 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$. It is assumed here that the values for the probability of requiring n cycles to isolate and reconfigure from a fault (p_n), obtained from fault injection experiments on the FTMP, apply to the hypothetical TMR system.

CONCLUSIONS

It is evident from the discussion in this paper that the *simplex sourcing of error-latch data* is a weak link for systems depending on this feature for fault recovery in a noisy environment and/or with design flaws. The unpredicted interaction between hardware, software, and faults can bring

forth new, and most likely anomalous, behavior from the systems.

As seen in the last section, fault injection can help detect and analyze the behavior of a system in the ultra-reliable regime. Although fault injection testing cannot be exhaustive, it has been demonstrated here that it provides a unique capability to unmask problems and to characterize the behavior of a fault tolerant system. Fault injection experiments excited the first symptoms of anomalous behavior in the FTMP. In view of the results obtained for FTMP, it can be concluded that fault injection experiments can provide very useful characterization data on the behavior of fault-tolerant systems.

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